

SILK ROAD SPIRIT IN MODERN BUKHARA

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Abstract. *Bukhara played an important role not only in Islamic civilization but also in trade on the Great Silk Road. Merchants from different countries came to the huge caravanserai in Bukhara, and this was a great impetus for the development of trade. This article analyzes the historical, economic and cultural role of the city of Bukhara, one of the important centers of the Great Silk Road. The study highlights the fact that Bukhara is located at the crossroads of trade routes connecting the East and the West, its importance in the development of caravan trade, crafts and financial relations. It also examines the role of Bukhara not only as a trade center, but also as a center of science, religious-educational and cultural exchange. The article reveals how the exchange of silk, spices, valuables and scientific ideas took place in Bukhara, based on historical sources, tourist records and modern scientific research. The results of the study show that Bukhara created a stable economic environment in the system of the Great Silk Road and was an important intermediary in strengthening cultural dialogue between different civilizations. This article serves to further understand the place of Bukhara in the development of world civilization.*

Keywords: *Silk Road, Bukhara, Trade, Culture, Religion, Spices, Caravans.*

Абстракт. *В данной статье анализируется историческая, экономическая и культурная роль города Бухары, одного из важных центров Великого Шелкового пути. Исследование подчеркивает тот факт, что Бухара расположена на пересечении торговых путей, соединяющих Восток и Запад, ее значение в развитии караванной торговли, ремесел и финансовых связей. Также рассматривается роль Бухары не только как торгового центра, но и как центра науки, религиозно-образовательного и культурного обмена. Статья раскрывает, как происходил обмен шелком, пряностями, ценностями и научными идеями в Бухаре, основываясь на исторических источниках, туристических записях и современных научных исследованиях. Результаты исследования показывают, что Бухара создала стабильную экономическую среду в системе Великого Шелкового пути и была важным посредником в укреплении культурного диалога между различными цивилизациями. Данная статья способствует дальнейшему пониманию места Бухары в развитии мировой цивилизации.*

Ключевые слова: *Шелковый путь, Бухара, торговля, культура, религия, специи, караваны.*

Abstract. *Ushbu maqolada Ipak yo‘lining asosiy markazi bo‘lgan Buxoroning tarixiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy roli tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda Buxoroning Sharq va G‘arbni bog‘laydigan savdo yo‘llari chorrahasida joylashganligi va karvon savdosi, hunarmandchilik hamda moliyaviy aloqalarni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati ta’kidlangan. Shuningdek, Buxoroning nafaqat*

savdo markazi, balki ilm-fan, diniy, ta'lim va madaniy almashinuv markazi sifatidagi roli ham o'rganiladi. Maqolada tarixiy manbalar, sayohat yozuvlari va zamonaviy ilmiy tadqiqotlarga tayanib, Buxoroda ipak, ziravorlar, qimmatbaho buyumlar va ilmiy g'oyalar almashinuvi o'rganiladi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, Buxoro Ipak yo'li tizimida barqaror iqtisodiy muhit yaratgan va turli sivilizatsiyalar o'rtasida madaniy muloqotni rivojlantirishda muhim vositachi bo'lib xizmat qilgan. Ushbu maqola Buxoroning jahon sivilizatsiyasi rivojidadagi o'rnini yanada chuqurroq tushunishga hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Ipak yo'li, Buxoro, savdo, madaniyat, din, ziravorlar, karvonlar.*

INTRODUCTION. Bukhara, located in modern-day Uzbekistan, holds a significant place in the history of Islamic civilization. As a major city along the ancient Silk Road, Bukhara served as a hub for trade, intellectual exchange, and the development of Islamic scholarship. Bukhara, strategically located on the Silk Road, became an important trading center connecting the East and West. Its geographical position allowed it to flourish both economically and culturally. Bukhara is widely known in history as a center of religion, science and culture, in addition to its trade importance. Many scientists, poets, and religious statesmen lived in this city. In addition, large madrasahs, mosques and libraries located in Bukhara played an important role in the spread of Islamic education and scientific knowledge throughout the region. Through this Silk Road, people exchanged not only products, but also various ideas, traditions, languages and cultural values. Historical monuments located in Bukhara clearly reflect its rich cultural heritage and memorial beauty. Ark Fort, Poi Kalon complex is very famous and today tourists from all over the world come to see these madrasa complexes. Such historical places of ours preserve the historical heritage and spirit of the Great Silk Road.

MAIN PART. Over the centuries, Bukhara experienced the rule of different empires and dynasties, including the Arab Caliphate, the Samanids, and later, the Mongols and Timurids. These influences shaped the city's history and contributed to its diverse heritage. Bukhara's location played a crucial role in its emergence as a prominent trading center. Situated in Central Asia, it served as a vital crossroads between different civilizations and regions. The city lay along one of the main branches of the Silk Road, a vast network of trade routes that connected China to the Mediterranean. Being at the intersection of multiple trade routes, Bukhara enjoyed access to a wide range of goods and resources from various parts of the world. (A. Gulyamov, 2024)

Bukhara was one of the most important centers of the Great Silk Road, serving as a crossroads of international trade, culture, and the Silk Road connecting the East and the West; important trade routes for silk, spices, and architecture passed through here, and the city of Bukhara achieved immense wealth and cultural prosperity through this trade, and now there is a settlement called "Great Silk Road" in the Bukhara region. (Sh. Bobojonov, 2025)

The region also attaches great importance to the development of domestic tourism, since many people have not had the opportunity to see and enjoy the historical monuments reflecting the history of our country, as well as the structures built after our republic gained independence. Taking this into account, tourist routes have been prepared that include the cities of Tashkent, Samarkand, Khiva, Shahrisabz, and Bukhara of our beloved republic. Separate routes have been developed to bring the population of our republic and region to visit 7 ancient monuments located in the Bukhara region. I am happy to have had the honor of seeing ancient Bukhara, where great thinkers grew up, - says Brazilian Nazaret Serpa. - I was very impressed by the freedom of the city. The high quality and uniqueness of the applied art samples created by

national masters and craftsmen presented at the "Asrlar sadosi" festival are worthy of admiration. I witnessed that all work in Uzbekistan serves, first of all, to ensure the interests of the people. As everyone knows, Bukhara is one of the tourist centers of Uzbekistan. According to the "Uzbek tourism" Central Committee, in 2012, more than 100,000 foreign tourists visited Bukhara. Sources indicate that more than 1 million tourists (not only foreign tourists) visited Bukhara. The total number of tourists was 903,000 in 2007, 1,069,000 in 2008, 1,215,000 in 2009, and 975,000 in 2010. (A. Abdullayev, 2025)

CONCLUSION. The city of Bukhara occupied a special place in the history of the Great Silk Road not only as an important trading center, but also as one of the main crossroads of cultural, religious, and scientific contacts between the East and the West. Its favorable geographical location, developed system of caravan routes, and trade infrastructure made Bukhara a major center of international trade for centuries. Silk, spices, precious stones, and other products passing through the city not only accelerated economic development but also created the basis for interaction and exchange of experience between different peoples and civilizations.

During the Silk Road, Bukhara was not limited only to the exchange of material wealth, but also played an important role in the spread of science, architecture, literature, and religious ideas. Madrasahs, mosques, and libraries turned the city into a major center of enlightenment, strengthening its influence throughout the region. It is these processes that led to Bukhara being included in the list of the "Holy Cities of the East".

Even today, Bukhara's historical heritage associated with the Great Silk Road has not lost its significance. This rich historical experience serves as an important source for the development of modern tourism, strengthening cultural diplomacy, and understanding national identity. Thus, Bukhara's place on the Silk Road is not only a phenomenon related to the past, but also has important strategic and cultural significance for present and future development.

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